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Inadequate Literacy Skills in the Italian Regions in the Period 2018-2022

It grew by an average of 12.56% between 2018 and 2022

Istat calculates the alphabetic competence as inadequate. The variable considers students in classes III of lower secondary school. The value is calculated as the percentage of students in classes III of lower secondary school who do not reach a sufficient level (Level I + Level II of 5 levels) of alphabetic competence. Invalsi provides the data as part of the national learning surveys. The data refers to the period between 2018 and 2022. Data relating to the 2020 financial year is missing. The reference to Trentino Alto Adige is also absent in the dataset.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of inadequate alphabetic competence in 2022. Sicily is in first place among the Italian regions for value of inadequate alphabetic competence in 2022 with a value of 51.3 units, followed by Calabria with a value of 51 units and from Campania with an amount of 48 units. In the middle of the table are Liguria with an amount of 38.6 units, followed by Lazio with a value of 36.1 units and Tuscany with an amount of 36 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia closes the ranking with an amount of 32.1 units, followed by Umbria with an amount of 30.2 units and Valle d'Aosta with a value of 27.5 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of the percentage change in inadequate alphabetic competence between 2018 and 2022. Friuli Venezia Giulia is in first place by value of the percentage change in inadequate alphabetic competence between 2018 and 2022 with a value equal to 25.39% or a variation from an amount of 25.60 units up to a value of 32.10 units or a variation equal to an amount of 6.50 units. Liguria follows with a value of 21.00% equal to a variation from 31.90 units up to a value of 38.60 units or a variation equal to 6.70 units. Below is Lombardy with a value equal to 20.96% equal to a variation from an amount of 27.20 units up to a value of 32.90 units or equal to an amount of 5.70 units.

In the middle of the ranking is Tuscany with a variation equal to an amount of 14.65% equal to a variation from an amount of 31.40 up to 36.00 units or equal to a value of 4.60 units. Veneto follows with a value of 13.99% with a variation from an amount of 28.60 units up to a value of 32.60 units or equal to an amount of 4.00 units. Still in the middle of the ranking, Abruzzo follows with a variation equal to an amount of 12.30% equivalent to a variation from an amount of 31.70 units up to a value of 35.60 units or a variation equal to a value of 3.90 units.

Umbria closes the ranking with a value of 5.96% with a variation from an amount of 28.50 units up to a value of 30.20 units equal to an amount of 1.70 units. Basilicata follows with a variation equal to an amount of 4.71% equal to an amount from 38.20 units up to a value of 40.00 units equal to an amount of 1.80 units. Valle d'Aosta closes the ranking with a variation of 3.00% or from an amount of 26.70 units up to a value of 27.50 units or equal to an amount of 0.80 units.

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Inadequate alphabetic competence in the Italian macro-regions between 2018 and 2022. Inadequate alphabetic competence grew in Northern Italy by an amount equal to 18.12% between 2018 and 2022, going from an amount of 28.70 units up to a value of 33.90 units. The inadequate alphabetic competence in Central Italy grew from an amount of 30.60 units up to a value of 35.20 units or equal to an amount of 15.03% equivalent to an amount of 4.60 units. Inadequate literacy skills grew in the South by 8.35%, i.e. from an amount of 43.10 in 2018 to 46.70 in 2022.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. A clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient is presented below. Two clusters are identified:

- *Cluster 1*: Umbria, Veneto, Emilia Romagna, Lombardy, Piedmont, Marche, Lazio, Valle d'Aosta, Tuscany, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Abruzzo, Liguria, Molise;
- *Cluster 2*: Campania, Sicily, Calabria, Sardinia, Puglia, Basilicata.

We can therefore see that the dominant cluster is Cluster 2. The ordering of the clusters is therefore made up of C2>C1. The regions of Southern Italy lead the Italian regions in terms of inadequate literacy skills. The only two southern regions that are part of cluster 1 are Abruzzo and Molise. We can therefore note that students from southern schools have performances in terms of alphabetic competence that are much lower than the corresponding values of students from Central-Northern Italy.

Conclusions. The value of inadequate literacy skills has grown in all Italian regions. On average between 2018 and 2022 the value of inadequate literacy skills grew in the Italian regions by 12.56%. If we consider the Italian macro-regions it is possible to note that 46.70% of students in Southern Italy have inadequate literacy skills, compared to 35.20% in Central Italy and 33.90% in Northern Italy. However, if we look at the growth rates between 2018 and 2022 we note that the growth of students with inadequate literacy skills in Northern Italy was equal to 18.12%, compared to 15.03% in Central Italy and the same in Southern Italy. at an amount of 8.35%. Two phenomena are therefore detectable:

- Almost half of southern students have inadequate literacy skills;
- Central Italy and Northern Italy are converging at high speed towards the levels of Southern Italy.

From a metric point of view, the total inefficiency of the school and education system in all Italian regions and macro-regions is therefore certified. If the objective of educational institutions is to increase the cognitive ability of the population then it is possible to state that the educational system has substantially failed for at least 47% of students in Southern Italy, 35.20% in Central Italy and 33.90% in Northern Italy. It is therefore necessary to intervene with new education policies that also make use of new digital technologies to increase literacy skills in the Italian regions.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Competenza Alfabetica non Adeguata nelle Regioni Italiane tra il 2018 ed il 2022

Rank	Regione	2018	2019	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
1	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	☆ 25,60	☆ 28,30	☆ 32,00	☆ 32,10	★ 6,50	☆ 25,39
2	<i>Liguria</i>	☆ 31,90	☆ 32,40	☆ 37,50	☆ 38,60	★ 6,70	☆ 21,00
3	<i>Lombardia</i>	☆ 27,20	☆ 29,10	☆ 33,60	☆ 32,90	★ 5,70	☆ 20,96
4	<i>Molise</i>	☆ 33,30	☆ 34,10	☆ 37,80	☆ 39,90	★ 6,60	☆ 19,82
5	<i>Marche</i>	☆ 27,50	☆ 28,30	☆ 31,70	☆ 32,50	★ 5,00	☆ 18,18
6	<i>Piemonte</i>	☆ 30,40	☆ 31,80	☆ 35,90	☆ 35,70	★ 5,30	☆ 17,43
7	<i>Lazio</i>	☆ 31,20	☆ 32,20	☆ 35,50	☆ 36,10	★ 4,90	☆ 15,71
8	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	☆ 30,30	☆ 31,70	☆ 34,50	☆ 34,80	★ 4,50	☆ 14,85
9	<i>Toscana</i>	☆ 31,40	☆ 32,50	☆ 35,70	☆ 36,00	★ 4,60	☆ 14,65
10	<i>Veneto</i>	☆ 28,60	☆ 29,60	☆ 32,20	☆ 32,60	★ 4,00	☆ 13,99
11	<i>Abruzzo</i>	☆ 31,70	☆ 33,00	☆ 36,00	☆ 35,60	★ 3,90	☆ 12,30
12	<i>Puglia</i>	☆ 38,30	☆ 38,30	☆ 42,00	☆ 42,50	★ 4,20	☆ 10,97
13	<i>Sardegna</i>	☆ 39,90	☆ 40,00	☆ 45,90	☆ 44,20	★ 4,30	☆ 10,78
14	<i>Sicilia</i>	☆ 47,30	☆ 47,60	☆ 50,50	☆ 51,30	★ 4,00	☆ 8,46
15	<i>Campania</i>	☆ 45,00	☆ 44,90	☆ 48,80	☆ 48,00	★ 3,00	☆ 6,67
16	<i>Calabria</i>	☆ 48,00	☆ 49,00	☆ 51,00	☆ 51,00	★ 3,00	☆ 6,25
17	<i>Umbria</i>	☆ 28,50	☆ 29,60	☆ 32,60	☆ 30,20	★ 1,70	☆ 5,96
18	<i>Basilicata</i>	☆ 38,20	☆ 37,90	☆ 41,20	☆ 40,00	★ 1,80	☆ 4,71
19	<i>Valle d'Aosta</i>	☆ 26,70	☆ 29,00	☆ 30,80	☆ 27,50	★ 0,80	☆ 3,00

Competenza Alfabetica non Adeguata nelle Macro-Regioni Italiane

Macro-Regioni	2018	2019	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
<i>Nord</i>	★ 28,70	★ 30,20	★ 34,00	★ 33,90	★ 5,20	★ 18,12
<i>Centro</i>	★ 30,60	★ 31,60	★ 34,90	★ 35,20	★ 4,60	★ 15,03
<i>Mezzogiorno</i>	★ 43,10	★ 43,30	★ 47,20	★ 46,70	★ 3,60	★ 8,35